

neurofibromin 2 / mosein-ezrin-radixin-like (MERLIN) tumor suppressor (NF2) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : NF2 is a critical regulator of contact-dependent inhibition of proliferation and functions at the interface between cell-cell adhesion, transmembrane signaling, and the actin cytoskeleton (Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man, OMIM[®]. Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD. MIM Number: 607379; Date last edited: 07/26/2023. World Wide Web URL: <https://omim.org/> Hamosh et al. [1]). Genetic alterations in NF2, located in chromosome 22, were the first genetic discoveries causing meningiomas. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [2] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [3], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of NF2, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed

*ML dicoveries of NF2 synergy in Meningiomas

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at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: NF2, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [4]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [5]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [6] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [7], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [8] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [13] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [9]. Finally, Cushing [10] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [11] and Pamir et al. [12]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. neurofibromin 2 / moesin-ezrin-radixin-like (MERLIN) tumor suppressor (NF2)

At least eight provisional categories of neurofibromatosis have been proposed. Among these, neurofibromatosis 1 (von Recklinghausen's disease or peripheral neurofibromatosis) and neurofibromatosis 2 (central or bilateral acoustic neurofibromatosis) have been established as distinct disorders. Wertelecki et al. [14] studied 15 affected male and 8 affected female members of one large kindred with neurofibromatosis 2. None of the patients met the diagnostic criteria for neurofibromatosis 1. Their simultaneous analysis of D22S1 and IGLV DNA markers for coinheritance with neurofibromatosis 2 indicated that the locus for the disease was near the center of the long arm of chromosome 22 (22q11.1 – >22q13.1). They hypothesized that this eventual isolation of the disease gene may reveal a cause of the most common intracranial tumors in humans.

Neurofibromatosis 2 (NF2) is a dominantly inherited disorder characterized by the occurrence of bilateral vestibular schwannomas and other central nervous system tumors including multiple meningiomas. Trofatter et al. [15] identified a candidate gene for the NF2 tumor suppressor that had suffered nonoverlapping deletions in DNA from two independent NF2 families and alterations in meningiomas from two unrelated NF2 patients. They observed that the candidate gene encoded a 587 amino acid protein with striking similarity to several members of a family of proteins proposed to link cytoskeletal components with proteins in the cell membrane. Further, to identify the genetic defect, Rouleau et al. [16] cloned the region between two flanking polymorphic markers on chromosome 22 and identified several genes. One was the site of germ-line mutations in NF2 patients and of somatic mutations in NF2-related tumours. They found that its deduced product had homology with proteins at the plasma membrane and cytoskeleton interface, a previously unknown site of action of tumour suppressor genes in humans.

Using recombinant inbred mice, Claudio et al. [17] determined the chromosomal position of the mouse homologue of the NF2 gene. Their analysis of the allele distribution in AKXD recombinant inbred strains using a simple sequence repeat polymorphism (D11Mcg1) in the 3' untranslated region of the mouse cDNA, mapped the mouse NF2 gene to the proximal region of chromosome 11, that is closely linked to Pmv-2. It was observed that this region also contained the genes for leukemia inhibitory factor and neurofilament heavy-chain polypeptide and thus represented a region of conserved synteny between human chromosome 22 and mouse chromosome 11. Using additional polymorphic markers, they established the following locus order from the centromere: D11Mit1 / D11Mit72 / D11Mcg1-D11Mit74-Pmv-2-D11Mi t2-D11Mit77 / D11Mit78 / D11Mit63.

Merlin (the neurofibromatosis 2 (NF2) gene product), is a tumor suppressor protein mutated in schwannomas and several other tumors and it shares significant homology with the actin-associated proteins ezrin, radixin and moesin (ERM proteins), to inhibit cell growth when overexpressed in cell lines. The similarities between merlin and ERM proteins suggest that merlin's growth-regulatory capabilities may be due to alterations in cytoskeletal function. Gutmann et al. [18] examined this possibility in rat schwannoma cell lines that overexpressed wild-type merlin isoforms and mutant merlin proteins and found that the overexpression of wild-type merlin resulted in transient

alterations in F-actin organization, cell spreading and cell attachment. Measurement in an in vitro motility assay indicated that merlin overexpression also impaired cell motility. These effects were only observed in cells overexpressing a merlin isoform capable of inhibiting cell growth and not with mutant merlin molecules (NF2 patient mutations) or a merlin splice variant (isoform II) lacking growth-inhibitory activity. Their data indicated that merlin may function to maintain normal cytoskeletal organization, and suggested that merlin's influence on cell growth depended on specific cytoskeletal rearrangements.

In an effort to gain insights into the function of the NF2 gene product, merlin or schwannomin, Gutmann et al. [19] performed a detailed functional analysis of eight naturally occurring non-conservative missense mutations in the NF2 gene. Using a regulatable expression system in rat schwannoma cells, they analyzed proliferation, actin cytoskeleton-mediated events and merlin folding and demonstrated that mutations clustered in the predicted alpha-helical region did not impair the function of merlin whereas those in either the N- or C-terminus of the protein rendered merlin inactive as a negative growth regulator. Their results suggested that the key functional domains of merlin lie within the highly conserved FERM domain and the unique C-terminus of the protein.

Northern blot analysis had shown that the human neurofibromatosis type 2 (NF2) cDNA hybridized to multiple RNA species. To examine whether these hybridizing RNA species represented NF2 transcripts, Chang et al. [20] cloned the complete NF2 cDNA by a combination of techniques and showed that human NF2 transcripts initiated at multiple positions.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to

the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [3], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [21] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [22] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [22].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [2]

Patel et al. [2] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [23]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [2]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with

a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [24], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [21] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [21]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [25], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these

25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the non-linearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [3].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. NF2 related synergies

Note - NF2 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [2]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2^{nd} order combinations of NF2 were recorded.

3.1.1. NF2 - MGST1 / ECE1 / TUBA4A / FLNC / FAM91A1

NF2 encodes for the protein Merlin and loss or mutation of the tumour suppressor Merlin predisposes individuals to develop multiple nervous system tumours, including schwannomas and meningiomas. Unbiased omics studies have become pivotal in the

identification of differentially expressed genes and proteins that may act as drug targets or biomarkers. Bassiri et al. [26] analysed the proteome and phospho-proteome of these genetically defined tumours using primary human tumour cells to identify upregulated/activated proteins and/or pathways. They identified over 2000 proteins in comparative experiments between Merlin-deficient schwannoma and meningioma compared to human Schwann and meningeal cells respectively, which is the first comprehensive assessment of the NF2-related meningioma and schwannoma proteome and phospho-proteome.

Based on the data provided by Bassiri et al. [26], microsomal glutathione S-transferase 1 (MGST1) protein was (+ively), endothelin converting enzyme 1 (ECE1) protien (-ively), tubulin alpha 4a (TUBA4A) phosphoprotein (+viely) , filamin C (FLNC) protein (+ively) and family with sequence similarity 91 member A1 (FAM91A1) phosphoprotein (-ively), expressed in Merlin-deficient cells. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of NF2 with MGST1 / ECE1 / TUBA4A / FLNC / FAM91A1, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [2].

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t NF2. MGST1 - NF2 shows high ranking of 172 (laplace), 230 (linear) and 224 (jansen); ECE1 - NF2 shows high ranking of 173 (laplace), 131 (rbf) and 227 (jansen); TUBA4A - NF2 shows high ranking of 156 (laplace), 249 (linear) and 199 (rbf); FLNC - NF2 shows high ranking of 155 (linear) and 223 (rbf); and FAM91A1 - NF2 shows high ranking of 130 (laplace), 99 (linear) and 291 (rbf).

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS NF2				
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T NF2				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
MGST1 - NF2	172	230	45	224
ECE1 - NF2	173	2	131	227
TUBA4A - NF2	156	249	199	43
FLNC - NF2	86	155	223	64
FAM91A1 - NF2	130	99	291	71

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between NF2 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t NF2 with NF2 – > MGST1 / ECE1 / TUBA4A / FLNC / FAM91A1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t NF2

MGST1	NF2
ECE1	NF2
TUBA4A	NF2
FLNC	NF2
FAM91A1	NF2

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between NF2 and Individual members.

3.1.2. NF2/Merlin and the Hippo signaling pathway components

NF2 encodes for the protein Merlin and loss or mutation of the tumour suppressor Merlin predisposes individuals to develop multiple nervous system tumours, including schwannomas and meningiomas. The conserved Hippo signaling pathway regulates organ size in *Drosophila* and mammals. The signaling cascade leading from the protein kinase Hippo (Hpo) (Mst1 and Mst2 in mammals) to the transcription coactivator Yorkie (Yki) (YAP in mammals) has been established, while the upstream regulators of the Hippo kinase cascade are less well defined, especially in mammals. Using conditional knockout mice, Zhang et al. [27] demonstrated that the Merlin/NF2 tumor suppressor and the YAP oncoprotein function antagonistically to regulate liver development. It was observed that inactivation of YAP led to loss of hepatocytes and biliary epithelial cells, while inactivation of NF2 led to hepatocellular carcinoma and bile duct hamartoma. Further, the NF2-deficient phenotypes in multiple tissues were largely suppressed by heterozygous deletion of YAP, suggesting that YAP is a major effector of Merlin/NF2 in growth regulation. Thus NF2/Merlin is an upregulator of Hippo signaling pathway that phosphorylates inhibits functions of transcriptional coactivator Yes-associated protein 1 (YAP1).

Recently, fusions between YAP1 and MAML2 have been identified in a subset of pediatric NF2 wild-type meningiomas. Szulzewsky et al. [28] showed that human YAP1-MAML2-positive meningiomas resemble NF2 mutant meningiomas by global and YAP-related gene expression signatures. They then go on to show that the expression of YAP1-MAML2 in mice induced tumors that resembled human YAP1 fusion-positive and NF2 mutant meningiomas by gene expression. Further, they demonstrated that YAP1-MAML2 primarily functioned by exerting TEAD-dependent YAP activity that is resistant to Hippo signaling. Treatment with YAP-TEAD inhibitors is sufficient to inhibit the viability of YAP1-MAML2-driven mouse tumors *ex vivo*. Finally, they showed that expression of constitutively active YAP1 (S127/397A-YAP1) is sufficient to induce similar tumors, suggesting that the YAP component of the gene fusion is the critical driver of these tumors. In summary, their results implicated YAP1-MAML2 as

a causal oncogenic driver and highlighted TEAD-dependent YAP activity as an oncogenic driver in YAP1-MAML2 fusion meningioma as well as NF2 mutant meningioma in general. To analyze the expression of YAP1-regulated genes in the different meningioma samples as well as in the pilocytic astrocytoma (PA) samples on a broader scale, they generated a data set of YAP1-regulated genes based on RNA-seq data that they had previously generated from human neural stem cells expressing an activated version of YAP1 [i.e S127/397A-(2SA)-YAP1; 1116 up-regulated and 1501 down-regulated genes compared with GFP-expressing control cells]. A log₂fold change cut-off of 0.58 (fold change of 50%) and FDR < 0.05 was used to find %transcriptionally regulated genes.

Note, that in 2019, at the time of release of data by Patel et al. [2], these YAP-regulated genes were not recorded. Szulzewsky et al. [28] recorded and released the data on these YAP-regulated genes in 2022. Thus, comparing the data for the foregoing papers, i was able to generate 2nd order combinations of NF2 with YAP-regulated genes. It would be interesting to see how these combinations rank and what further might be developed based on them.

Based on the data provided by Szulzewsky et al. [28], for, G protein-coupled receptor class C group 5 member A (GPRC5A) (+ive), FOS like 2, AP-1 transcription factor subunit (FOSL2) (+ive), molybdenum cofactor sulfurase (MOCOS) (+ive), calmodulin regulated spectrin associated protein family member 3 (CAMSAP3) (+ive), mesothelin (MSLN) (+ive), annexin A13 (ANXA13) (+ive), nicotinamide phosphoribosyltransferase (NAMPT) (+ive), sodium channel epithelial 1 subunit alpha (SCNN1A) (+ive), RNA binding motif protein 24 (RBM24) (+ive), melanophilin (MLPH) (+ive), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily C member 4 (KCNC4) (+ive), periplakin (PPL) (+ive), SH3 domain containing ring finger 2 (SH3RF2) (+ive), F-box protein 32 (FBXO32) (+ive), grainyhead like transcription factor 3 (GRHL3) (+ive), chloride intracellular channel 6 (CLIC6) (+ive), sphingomyelin synthase 2 (SGMS2) (+ive), FHF complex subunit HOOK interacting protein 1A (FAM160A1) (+ive), ankyrin repeat domain 33B (ANKRD33B) (+ive), serine peptidase inhibitor, Kunitz type 1 (SPINT1) (+ive), kallikrein related peptidase 10 (KLK10) (+ive), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 9 (TTC9) (+ive), lipocalin 2 (LCN2) (+ive), coiled-coil domain containing 68 (CCDC68) (+ive), RAB3B, member RAS oncogene family (RAB3B) (+ive), CDC42 binding protein kinase gamma (CDC42BPG) (+ive), membrane bound glycerophospholipid O-acyltransferase 1 (MBOAT1) (+ive), LRRN4 C-terminal like (LRRN4CL) (+ive), calpain 12 (CAPN12) (+ive), v-maf avian musculoaponeurotic fibrosarcoma oncogene homolog F (MAFF) (+ive), FAT atypical cadherin 4 (FAT4) (+ive) and collagen type XV alpha 1 chain (COL15A1) (+ive), log₂FoldChanges were recorded.

Similarly, for solute carrier family 4 member 4 (SLC4A4) (-ive), immunoglobulin superfamily member 9 (IGSF9) (-ive), spermine oxidase (SMOX) (-ive), PTPNM family member 3 (PTPNM3) (-ive), BMP and activin membrane bound inhibitor (BAMBI) (-ive), neurocalcin delta (NCALD) (-ive), myelin regulatory factor (MYRF) (-ive), G protein subunit alpha z (GNAZ) (-ive), leucine rich repeat containing 4 (LRRC4) (-ive), coiled-coil domain containing 136 (CCDC136) (-ive), argininosuccinate synthase 1 (ASS1) (-ive), KIAA0319 (-ive), FXFD domain containing ion transport regulator 6 (FXFD6) (-ive), HECT, C2 and WW domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 2 (HECW2) (-ive), HECT and RLD domain containing E3 ubiquitin pro-

tein ligase 5 (HERC5) (-ive), shisa like 1 (KIAA1644) (-ive), kinesin family member 21A (KIF21A) (-ive), collagen type II alpha 1 chain (COL2A1) (-ive), solute carrier family 47 member 1 (SLC47A1) (-ive), maelstrom spermatogenic transposon silencer (MAEL) (-ive), immunoglobulin like domain containing receptor 2 (ILDR2) (-ive), cellular retinoic acid binding protein 2 (CRABP2) (-ive), immunoglobulin superfamily member 11 (IGSF11) (-ive), serine protease 35 (PRSS35) (-ive), coiled-coil domain containing 3 (CCDC3) (-ive), chondrolectin (CHODL) (-ive), neural cell adhesion molecule 2 (NCAM2) (-ive), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein like (PHYHIPL) (-ive), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit beta 2 (CACNB2) (-ive), sodium voltage-gated channel beta subunit 3 (SCN3B) (-ive), ubiquitin specific peptidase 54 (USP54) (-ive), reprimin, TP53 dependent G2 arrest mediator homolog (RPRM) (-ive), WSC domain containing 1 (WSCD1) (-ive), synemin (SYNM) (-ive), limbic system associated membrane protein (LSAMP) (-ive), potassium voltage-gated channel interacting protein 4 (KCNIP4) (-ive), and glycoprotein M6B (GPM6B) (-ive), \log_2 FoldChanges were recorded.

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of NF2 with these YAP-regulated genes, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [2].

Table 3 and 4 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 5 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3 and 4. The table 3 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t NF2. GPRC5A - NF2 shows high ranking of 145 (laplace) 266 (linear) 37 281 (jansen); FOSL2 - NF2 18 173 (linear) 304 (rbf) 107 (jansen); MOCOS - NF2 38 300 (linear) 298 (rbf) 122 (jansen); CAMSAP3 - NF2 shows high ranking of 181 (laplace) 59 125 (rbf) 306 (jansen); MSLN - NF2 shows high ranking of 291 (laplace) 168 (linear) 86 137 (jansen); ANXA13 - NF2 shows high ranking of 179 (laplace) 287 (linear) 16 228 (jansen); SCNN1A - NF2 shows high ranking of 203 (laplace) 88 251 (rbf) 108 (jansen); MLPH - NF2 shows high ranking of 237 (laplace) 299 (linear) 119 136 (jansen); KCNC4 - NF2 shows high ranking of 215 (laplace) 110 (linear) 163 (rbf) 63; GRHL3 - NF2 shows high ranking of 187 (laplace) 167 (linear) 115 259 (jansen); CLIC6 - NF2 shows high ranking of 261 (laplace) 5 165 (rbf) 220 (jansen); FAM160A1 - NF2 shows high ranking of 148 (laplace) 274 (linear) 241 (rbf) 32; KLK10 - NF2 shows high ranking of 271 (laplace) 256 (linear) 75 129 (jansen); LCN2 - NF2 shows high ranking of 252 (laplace) 294 (linear) 143 (rbf) 225 (jansen); CCDC68 - NF2 shows high ranking of 301 (laplace) 177 (linear) 24 151 (jansen); RAB3B - NF2 shows high ranking of 209 (laplace) 301 (linear) 137 (rbf) 258 (jansen); LRRN4CL - NF2 shows high ranking of 143 (laplace) 138 (linear) 178 (rbf) 282 (jansen); MAFF - NF2 shows high ranking of 123 (laplace) 176 (linear) 124 296 (jansen); and FAT4 - NF2 shows high ranking of 194 (laplace) 106 (linear) 274 (rbf) 291 (jansen).

On the contrary, the following showed low ranking combinations, i.e NAMPT - NF2 5 44 253 103; RBM24 - NF2 89 38 173 1; SH3RF2 - NF2 33 10 247 78; FBXO32 - NF2 198 56 21 204; SGMS2 - NF2 92 151 295 286; ANKRD33B - NF2 50 46 222 83; SPINT1 - NF2 30 132 107 244; TTC9 - NF2 41 165 212 241; CDC42BPG - NF2 36 91 145 44; MBOAT1 - NF2 28 54 228 22; CAPN12 - NF2 101 74 181 51; and COL15A1 - NF2 287 255 51 38.

The table 4 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t NF2. SLC4A4 - NF2

shows high ranking of 46 247 (linear) 265 (rbf) 214 (jansen); IGSF9 - NF2 shows high ranking of 127 (laplace) 199 (linear) 168 (rbf) 239 (jansen); PITPNM3 - NF2 shows high ranking of 231 (laplace) 185 (linear) 91 256 (jansen); MYRF - NF2 shows high ranking of 255 (laplace) 225 (linear) 71 238 (jansen); LRRC4 - NF2 shows high ranking of 220 (laplace) 295 (linear) 209 (rbf) 53; CCDC136 - NF2 shows high ranking of 54 153 (linear) 292 (rbf) 192 (jansen); FXYD6 - NF2 shows high ranking of 256 (laplace) 147 (linear) 132 (rbf) 246 (jansen); HECW2 - NF2 shows high ranking of 166 (laplace) 107 (linear) 229 (rbf) 10; HERC5 - NF2 shows high ranking of 53 114 (linear) 171 (rbf) 150 (jansen); KIAA1644 - NF2 shows high ranking of 267 (laplace) 108 (linear) 166 (rbf) 18; COL2A1 - NF2 shows high ranking of 204 (laplace) 272 (linear) 186 (rbf) 236 (jansen); MAEL - NF2 shows high ranking of 305 (laplace) 186 (linear) 83 156 (jansen); ILDR2 - NF2 shows high ranking of 283 (laplace) 208 (linear) 12 153 (jansen); IGSF11 - NF2 shows high ranking of 91 180 (linear) 191 (rbf) 247 (jansen); CHODL - NF2 shows high ranking of 244 (laplace) 164 (linear) 126 (rbf) 235 (jansen); NCAM2 - NF2 shows high ranking of 102 (laplace) 163 (linear) 138 (rbf) 226 (jansen); RPRM - NF2 shows high ranking of 269 (laplace) 228 (linear) 54 135 (jansen); and GPM6B - NF2 shows high ranking of 161 (laplace) 257 (linear) 147 (rbf) 199 (jansen).

On the contrary, the following showed low ranking combinations, i.e SMOX - NF2 2 90 146 197; BAMBI - NF2 64 65 235 58; NCALD - NF2 99 83 187 98; GNAZ - NF2 193 9 66 106; ASS1 - NF2 71 47 262 79; KIAA0319 - NF2 88 30 264 57; KIF21A - NF2 11 118 109 292; SLC47A1 - NF2 17 181 34 260; CRABP2 - NF2 58 48 89 277; PRSS35 - NF2 1 267 248 56; CCDC3 - NF2 74 220 25 93; PHYHIPL - NF2 35 57 245 26; CACNB2 - NF2 20 92 174 68; SCN3B - NF2 135 8 208 11; USP54 - NF2 27 160 270 48; WSCD1 - NF2 51 40 219 127; SYNM - NF2 96 79 64 289; LSAMP - NF2 213 29 33 230; and KCNIP4 - NF2 307 261 3 143.

RANKING HIPPO SIGNALING PATHWAY COMPONENTS VS NF2									
RANKING OF HIPPO SIGNALING PATHWAY COMPONENTS W.R.T NF2									
DEGs U5 HUMAN NEURAL STEM CELLS EXPRESSING S127/397A-YAP1					VERSUS GFP WITH +IVE LOG ₂ FC				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
GPRC5A - NF2	145	266	37	281	FOSL2 - NF2	18	173	304	107
MOCOS - NF2	38	300	298	122	CAMSAP3 - NF2	181	59	125	306
MSLN - NF2	291	168	86	137	ANXA13 - NF2	179	287	16	228
NAMPT - NF2	5	44	253	103	SCNN1A - NF2	203	88	251	108
RBM24 - NF2	89	38	173	1	MLPH - NF2	237	299	119	136
KCNC4 - NF2	215	110	163	63	SH3RF2 - NF2	33	10	247	78
FBXO32 - NF2	198	56	21	204	GRHL3 - NF2	187	167	115	259
CLIC6 - NF2	261	5	165	220	SGMS2 - NF2	92	151	295	286
FAM160A1 - NF2	148	274	241	32	ANKRD33B - NF2	50	46	222	83
SPINT1 - NF2	30	132	107	244	KLK10 - NF2	271	256	75	129
TTC9 - NF2	41	165	212	241	LCN2 - NF2	252	294	143	225
CCDC68 - NF2	301	177	24	151	RAB3B - NF2	209	301	137	258
CDC42BPG - NF2	36	91	145	44	MBOAT1 - NF2	28	54	228	22
LRRN4CL - NF2	143	138	178	282	CAPN12 - NF2	101	74	181	51
MAFF - NF2	123	176	124	296	FAT4 - NF2	194	106	274	291
COL15A1 - NF2	287	255	51	38					

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between NF2 VS Hippo signaling pathway components.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influ-

RANKING HIPPO SIGNALING PATHWAY COMPONENTS VS NF2									
RANKING OF HIPPO SIGNALING PATHWAY COMPONENTS W.R.T NF2									
DEGs U5 HUMAN NEURAL STEM CELLS EXPRESSING S127/397A-YAP1 VERSUS GFP WITH -IVE LOG ₂ FC									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
SLC4A4 - NF2	46	247	265	214	IGSF9 - NF2	127	199	168	239
SMOX - NF2	2	90	146	197	PITPNM3 - NF2	231	185	91	256
BAMBI - NF2	64	65	235	58	NCALD - NF2	99	83	187	98
MYRF - NF2	255	225	71	238	GNAZ - NF2	193	9	66	106
LRRC4 - NF2	220	295	209	53	CCDC136 - NF2	54	153	292	192
ASS1 - NF2	71	47	262	79	KIAA0319 - NF2	88	30	264	57
FXVD6 - NF2	256	147	132	246	HECW2 - NF2	166	107	229	10
HERC5 - NF2	53	114	171	150	KIAA1644 - NF2	267	108	166	18
KIF21A - NF2	11	118	109	292	COL2A1 - NF2	204	272	186	236
SLC47A1 - NF2	17	181	34	260	MAEL - NF2	305	186	83	156
ILDR2 - NF2	283	208	12	153	CRABP2 - NF2	58	48	89	277
IGSF11 - NF2	91	180	191	247	PRSS35 - NF2	1	267	248	56
CCDC3 - NF2	74	220	25	93	CHODL - NF2	244	164	126	235
NCAM2 - NF2	102	163	138	226	PHYHIPL - NF2	35	57	245	26
CACNB2 - NF2	20	92	174	68	SCN3B - NF2	135	8	208	11
USP54 - NF2	27	160	270	48	RPRM - NF2	269	228	54	135
WSCD1 - NF2	51	40	219	127	SYNM - NF2	96	79	64	289
LSAMP - NF2	213	29	33	230	KCNIP4 - NF2	307	261	3	143
GPM6B - NF2	161	257	147	199					

Table 4: 2nd order interaction ranking between NF2 VS Hippo signaling pathway components.

ences - • Individual members w.r.t NF2 with NF2 – > GPRC5A / FOSL2 / MOCOS / CAMSAP3 / MSLN / ANXA13 / SCNN1A / MLPH / KCNC4 / GRHL3 / CLIC6 / FAM160A1 / KLK10 / LCN2 / CCDC68 / RAB3B / LRRN4CL / MAFF / FAT4; and the results of the table 4 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t NF2 with NF2 – > SLC4A4 / IGSF9 / PITPNM3 / MYRF / LRRC4 / CCDC136 / FXVD6 / HECW2 / HERC5 / KIAA1644 / COL2A1 / MAEL / ILDR2 / IGSF11 / CHODL / NCAM2 / RPRM / GPM6B.

3.1.3. NF2/Merlin and the Hippo signaling pathway independent components

Apart from the Hippo signaling pathway, Merlin/NF2 also regulate other signaling pathways. A few components from other pathways were also recorded in the data by Patel et al. [2]. They are erb-b2 receptor tyrosine kinase 3 (ERBB3) and RasGEF domain family member 1B (RASGEF1B).

Thaxton et al. [29] showed that activation of ErbB2/ErbB3 receptors in primary rat Schwann cells by neuregulin-1 induced merlin phosphorylation at Ser518 via PKA. Further, Garcia and Gutmann [30] observed that there was elevation in ErbB2 activation in NF2-ependymomas. They also show that ErbB2 activation in mouse NF2-deficient spinal cord neural progenitor cells was caused by Rac-mediated retention of the receptor at the plasma membrane. Thaxton et al. [29] showed that Merlin re-expression in *Nf2*^{-/-} Schwann cells similarly reduced the transport of growth factor receptors ErbB2/ErbB3, insulin-like growth factor 1 receptor (IGF1R) and platelet-derived growth factor receptor (PDGFR).

The small G-protein Ras is a tightly controlled regulator of cell fate. Prolonged or persistent arrest in the activated GTP-loaded state by mutation of Ras as in lung

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t NF2	
Genes in S127/397A-YAP1 versus GFP with +ive log ₂ FC	
GPRC5A / FOSL2 / MOCOS / CAMSAP3	
/ MSLN / ANXA13 / SCNN1A / MLPH	
KCNC4 / GRHL3 / CLIC6 / FAM160A1	
KLK10 / LCN2 / CCDC68 / RAB3B	
LRRN4CL / MAFF / FAT4	NF2
Individual members w.r.t NF2	
Genes in S127/397A-YAP1 versus GFP with -ive log ₂ FC	
SLC4A4 / IGSF9 / PITPNM3 / MYRF	
LRRC4 / CCDC136 / FXYD6 / HECW2	
HERC5 / KIAA1644 / COL2A1 / MAEL	
ILDR2 / IGSF11 / CHODL / NCAM2	
RPRM / GPM6B	NF2

Table 5: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between NF2 and Hippo signaling pathway components.

cancer or in a RasGTPase-activating protein as in neurofibromatosis type 1 promotes tumorigenesis. Morrison et al. [31] showed that the tumor-suppressor protein merlin (mutated in NF2) also controlled Ras activity. But how merlin regulates Ras activity remained elusive. Cui et al. [32] demonstrated that merlin could directly interact with both Ras and p120RasGAP (also named RasGAP).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of NF2 with these genes, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [2].

Table 6 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 7 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 6. The table 6 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t NF2. RASGEF1B - NF2 showed high ranking of 131 (laplace), 264 (linear), 296 (rbf) and 202 (jansen); while ERBB3 - NF2 showed low ranking of 78 306 36 and 195.

One can also interpret the results of the table 6 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t NF2 with NF2 – > RASGEF1B.

3.1.4. NF2 unknown combinations with high ranking

Along with the above known genes affected by NF2, there are others genes that were upregulated and recorded in Patel et al. [2]. In document here, the 2nd order combinations with NF2, which were assigned high rank by the machine learning based search engine. These high ranks point to the possible existence of synergy between the NF2

RANKING HIPPO PATHWAY INDEPENDENT COMPONENTS VS NF2				
RANKING OF HIPPO PATHWAY INDEPENDENT MEMBERS W.R.T NF2				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
ERBB3 - NF2	78	306	36	195
RASGEF1B - NF2	131	264	296	202

Table 6: 2nd order interaction ranking between NF2 VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t NF2	
RASGEF1B	NF2

Table 7: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between NF2 and Individual members.

and the genetic factors, that might not have been explored till now. Further, wet lab tests will confirm the veracity of these rankings.

Of these, USH1 protein network component harmonin (USH1C), Rho GTPase activating protein 44 (ARHGAP44), tolloid like 1 (TLL1), neurite extension and migration factor (NEXMIF), ribosomal protein S6 kinase A6 (RPS6KA6), parathyroid hormone like hormone (PTH1H), ezrin (EZR), eukaryotic translation elongation factor 1 alpha 2 (EEF1A2), fms related receptor tyrosine kinase 1 (FLT1), tight junction protein 3 (TJP3), RUN domain containing 3B (RUNDC3B), mannosidase alpha class 1A member 1 (MAN1A1), interleukin 1 receptor like 1 (IL1RL1), SSX family member 2 interacting protein (SSX2IP), tetraspanin 1 (TSPAN1), interferon regulatory factor 6 (IRF6), phospholipid phosphatase related 4 (PLPPR4), cyclin and CBS domain divalent metal cation transport mediator 1 (CNNM1), lecithin retinol acyltransferase (LRAT), G protein signaling modulator 2 (GPSM2), myosin VC (MYO5C), LARGE xylosyl- and glucuronyltransferase 1 (LARGE1), coiled-coil domain containing 150 (CCDC150), atypical chemokine receptor 3 (ACKR3), coiled-coil domain 39 molecular ruler complex subunit (CCDC39), scavenger receptor cysteine rich family member with 4 domains (SSC4D), astrotactin 2 (ASTN2), inter-alpha-trypsin inhibitor heavy chain 2 (ITIH2), serine and arginine rich splicing factor 12 (SRSF12), nucleophosmin/nucleoplasmin 2 (NPM2), actin alpha cardiac muscle 1 (ACTC1), spondin 2 (SPON2), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6B2 (COX6B2), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 2 subunit (CHRN2), cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4 (CYP3A4), AKNA domain containing 1 (AKNAD1), sphingosine-1-phosphate phosphatase 2 (SGPP2), six transmembrane epithelial antigen of the prostate 1 metalloenductase (STEAP1), adenylate cyclase 1 (ADCY1), defensin beta 1 (DEFB1), aquaporin 3 (Gill blood group) (AQP3), serpin family B member 8 (SERPINB8), pleckstrin homology domain containing A7 (PLEKHA7), myosin IA (MYO1A), small G protein signaling modulator 1 (SGSM1), bradykinin receptor B2 (BDKRB2), mucin

3A, cell surface associated (MUC3A), DLG associated protein 1 (DLGAP1), cilia and flagella associated protein 46 (CFAP46), tryptase alpha/beta 1 (TPSAB1), bisphosphoglycerate mutase (BPGM), regulator of calcineurin 2 (RCAN2), syntrophin gamma 2 (SNTG2), leucine rich repeat and Ig domain containing 2 (LINGO2), myosin ID (MYO1D), transmembrane protein 125 (TMEM125), cadherin 4 (CDH4), receptor interacting serine/threonine kinase 4 (RIPK4), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member A3 (ALDH1A3), short chain dehydrogenase/reductase family 42E, member 1 (SDR42E1), transcobalamin 2 (TCN2), piccolo presynaptic cytomatrix protein (PCLO), BCR activator of RhoGEF and GTPase (BCR), natural killer cell cytotoxicity receptor 3 ligand 1 (NCR3LG1), family with sequence similarity 78 member B (FAM78B), solute carrier family 6 member 9 (SLC6A9), laminin subunit beta 3 (LAMB3), tryptase beta 2 (TPSB2), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 1 (ENPP1), AFDN divergent transcript (AFDN-DT), ankyrin repeat domain 35 (ANKRD35), sterol regulatory element binding transcription factor 2 (SREBF2) and chromosome 9 open reading frame 129 (C9orf129 / FAM120A2P), were found to be recorded as up-regulated in data by Patel et al. [2]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of NF2 with these genes.

Table 8 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 9 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 8. The table 8 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t NF2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 8 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t NF2 with NF2 – > USH1C / ARHGAP44 / TLL1 / NEXMIF / RPS6KA6 / PTHLH / EZR / EEF1A2 / FLT1 / TJP3 / RUNDC3B / MAN1A1 / IL1RL1 / SSX2IP / TSPAN1 / IRF6 / PLPPR4 / CNNM1 / LRAT / GPSM2 / MYO5C / LARGE1 / CCDC150 / ACKR3 / CCDC39 / SSC4D / ASTN2 / ITIH2 / SRSF12 / NPM2 / ACTC1 / SPON2 / COX6B2 / CHRNB2 / CYP3A4 / AKNAD1 / SGPP2 / STEAP1 / ADCY1 / DEFB1 / AQP3 / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 / MYO1A / SGSM1 / BDKRB2 / MUC3A / DLGAP1/ CFAP46 / TPSAB1 / BPGM / RCAN2 / SNTG2 / LINGO2 / MYO1D / TMEM125 / CDH4 / RIPK4 / ALDH1A3 / SDR42E1 / TCN2 / PCLO / BCR / NCR3LG1 / FAM78B / LAMB3 / TPSB2 / ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / ANKRD35 / SREBF2 / C9orf129.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic NF2 2^{nd} order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of NF2-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

RANKING UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS NF2									
RANKING OF UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T NF2									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
USH1C - NF2	284	223	56	159	ARHGAP44 - NF2	185	4	243	257
TLL1 - NF2	245	215	84	189	NEXMIF - NF2	65	196	255	179
RPS6KA6 - NF2	211	62	215	293	PTHLH - NF2	270	170	40	172
EZR - NF2	196	23	238	250	EEF1A2 - NF2	202	93	190	294
FLT1 - NF2	55	288	279	217	TJP3 - NF2	290	211	158	113
RUNDC3B - NF2	265	246	96	191	MAN1A1 - NF2	151	37	257	163
IL1RL1 - NF2	289	219	5	152	SSX2IP - NF2	175	111	256	233
TSPAN1 - NF2	304	207	15	194	IRF6 - NF2	212	148	188	169
PLPPR4 - NF2	248	187	14	161	CNNM1 - NF2	195	84	189	248
LRAT - NF2	262	302	161	70	GPSM2 - NF2	16	179	252	173
MYO5C - NF2	158	169	196	28	LARGE1 - NF2	21	210	239	210
CCDC150 - NF2	159	139	236	297	ACKR3 - NF2	205	285	117	255
CCDC39 - NF2	192	275	149	82	SSC4D - NF2	190	172	48	290
ASTN2 - NF2	39	258	210	208	ITIH2 - NF2	232	280	104	273
SRSF12 - NF2	160	41	200	200	NPM2 - NF2	23	195	194	276
ACTC1 - NF2	22	192	201	287	SPON2 - NF2	124	190	213	275
COX6B2 - NF2	227	245	49	155	CHRNA2 - NF2	68	202	225	270
CYP3A4 - NF2	201	127	227	206	AKNAD1 - NF2	218	175	118	234
SGPP2 - NF2	278	293	90	181	STEAP1 - NF2	134	289	217	288
ADCY1 - NF2	19	158	286	265	DEFB1 - NF2	294	212	1	171
AQP3 - NF2	302	162	26	216	SERPINB8 - NF2	95	284	242	183
PLEKHA7 - NF2	90	270	278	252	MYO1A - NF2	169	305	230	8
SGSM1 - NF2	44	268	220	190	BDKRB2 - NF2	254	188	79	209
MUC3A - NF2	292	233	42	149	DLGAP1 - NF2	229	178	74	221
CFAP46 - NF2	117	298	299	164	TPSAB1 - NF2	260	183	112	223
BPGM - NF2	208	72	297	170	RCAN2 - NF2	42	150	211	232
SNTG2 - NF2	303	201	72	167	LINGO2 - NF2	178	279	162	91
MYO1D - NF2	280	221	88	215	TMEM125 - NF2	233	229	159	280
CDH4 - NF2	282	184	28	174	RIPK4 - NF2	219	276	98	211
ALDH1A3 - NF2	258	200	32	212	SDR42E1 - NF2	191	213	136	205
TCN2 - NF2	180	253	231	218	PCLO - NF2	259	269	13	201
BCR - NF2	242	283	218	279	NCR3LG1 - NF2	253	204	240	50
FAM78B - NF2	293	237	202	21	SLC6A9 - NF2	238	105	249	272
LAMB3 - NF2	285	273	282	271	TPSB2 - NF2	225	34	271	166
ENPP1 - NF2	233	254	224	301	AFDN-DT - NF2	279	191	152	41
ANKRD35 - NF2	299	149	258	261	SREBF2 - NF2	157	146	157	180
C9orf129 - NF2	154	241	293	27					

Table 8: 2nd order interaction ranking between NF2 VS Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Unknown Individual members w.r.t NF2	
USH1C / ARHGAP44 / TLL1 / NEXMIF / RPS6KA6 ...	
PTHLH / EZR / EEF1A2 / FLT1 / TJP3 / RUNDC3B ...	
MAN1A1 / IL1RL1 / SSX2IP / TSPAN1 / IRF6 ...	
PLPPR4 / CNNM1 / LRAT / GPSM2 / MYO5C / LARGE1 ...	
CCDC150 / ACKR3 / CCDC39 / SSC4D / ASTN2 / ITIH2 ...	
SRSF12 / NPM2 / ACTC1 / SPON2 / COX6B2 / CHRNB2 ...	
CYP3A4 / AKNAD1 / SGPP2 / STEAP1 / ADCY1 / DEFB1 ...	
AQP3 / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 / MYO1A / SGSM1 / BDKRB2 ...	
MUC3A / DLGAP1 / CFAP46 / TPSAB1 / BPGM / RCAN2 ...	
SNTG2 / LINGO2 / MYO1D / TMEM125 / CDH4 / RIPK4 ...	
ALDH1A3 / SDR42E1 / TCN2 / PCLO / BCR / NCR3LG1 ...	
FAM78B / LAMB3 / TPSB2 / ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / ANKRD35 ...	
SREBF2 / C9orf129	NF2

Table 9: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between NF2 and Individual members.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [2]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

5. References

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